

ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICE IN PERSONAL LIFE

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Abstract. *This article addresses the issue of the organization of psychological services in today's globalization process to ensure the growth of a healthy person.*

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INTRODUCTION. In world psychology, attention is paid to the study of the problem of the organization of psychological services as a special research direction. In psychological researches, the pedagogic psychologist has studied all the work he can do for the comprehensive development of the social psychological service and its specific features. In this direction, attention is paid to the importance of applying and introducing psychological mechanisms representing various methods and modern technologies of psychological service organization. At the same time, situations such as the organization of psychological services and the elimination of personnel problems are considered urgent problems.

Today, a number of theoretical-scientific and practical-methodical works on the introduction of psychological services in educational systems are to a certain extent the basis for the introduction and development of psychological services. At the moment, the lack of special studies that comprehensively and deeply analyze the current state of the psychological service system and its practical activities and reveal the perspectives of the psychological service based on these analyzes remains an extremely important problem.

So, naturally, in order to eliminate this problem, it is necessary to conduct psychological and social psychological research dedicated to the study, analysis and interpretation of the introduction of psychological service in Uzbekistan, its current state and prospects for the development of the digital economy. Based on this, the fact that special researches related to scientific-organizational aspects of psychological service related to the preparation of future personnel in all aspects in today's educational institutions and labor teams, and especially to researching the possibilities of social-psychological protection, are extremely slow; social psychology, modern directions of psychological consultation sciences, the tasks covering today's psychological service implementation are not defined clearly and in detail, as an example of psychological service experiences organized in educational and labor institutions, social psychological protection in ensuring the successful activity of students and workers One of today's urgent problems can be noted the lack of development of scientific and practical recommendations that meet the requirements of Uzbekistan's independent and prospective path, socio-economic development, related to the study and improvement of its capabilities.

Literature analysis and methodology. Andreeva G.M. conducted research aimed at identifying social psychological tasks that are of great theoretical importance for the successful organization of psychological services. Davletshin M.G., Zabrodin Yu.M., Carnegi D., Karimova V.M., Parigin B.D., Shoumarov G'.B., G'oziev E.G'.; It is impossible to separate the practical psychology of a person, related to the traditions of the development of today's psychology, from his social activity and social nature in society.

From this point of view, the process of correct and effective management of human factors and its social processes in society requires the inevitability of providing psychological services to society and its members. In this regard, the practical problems of human psychology should be solved as a result of strong cooperation of economics, law, ethics, ethnography, history, sociology, and all such sciences. And the methodology of psychological service is mostly based on the foundations of the first direction - "psychological social psychology".

Discussion and results. The development of each science is directly related to the structure of methodological devices that reveal a scientific direction based on new evidence. Because there will be no clear practical results in the field without clear methodology. After all, another important new task of the science of social psychology (in terms of form is new, and in terms of content it is ours) is to define the scope of theoretical, practical and empirical research related to the methodology of psychological services. should be analyzed. As we know from special psychological literature, the general directions of the methodology of social psychological service can be explained as follows: the researches of representatives of Western social psychology can be explained as follows: W. Wundt's large (ten-volume) epic entitled "People's Psychology" published in 1900 His work served to illuminate the directions of social psychology and revealed the complex aspects of studying human spirituality, culture and ideology.

The theory of "social instincts of behavior" written in 1908 by the famous English psychologist William McDougall "Introduction to Social Psychology" served as the first basis for elucidating the problem of ensuring the harmony of human instincts and activities in opposition to Freudianism. The content of empirical studies conducted by B.M. Teplov, V.S. Merlin, V.D. Nebilitsyn, E.A. Golubeva, B.R. Kadirov and their students is the natural and innate qualities of each person (individual), the higher nervous activity, which is important for social psychology and social psychological service. created a great opportunity to perfectly study the elements of unique ability and the process of the organization of education, external environment and activities affecting it, and to determine the ways of its development on the basis of social goals.

These opportunities can serve as a basis for learning the buds of talent to perform one or another activity in a person and, on this basis, to perfect the activity of a person. In accordance with this, special research confirms that the successful organization of activities depends on individual characteristics, especially the temperament and individual style of each person. In particular, the development of a set of methods related to the observation, analysis and development of this condition in the course of labor and educational activities is evidence that the psychological service is an important task.

In particular, the empirical data of E.A. Klimov confirm that employees of the "mobile type" and "immobile type" of the nervous system can achieve the same high level of production success when working on several machines. The main reason for this is the ability to choose and implement different courses of action in the same work situation.

In general, according to the general opinions of the above-mentioned scientists, it is noted that an individual style does not appear immediately in a person, but often appears spontaneously (that is, with the help of individual-emotional qualities).

Therefore, if each person is approached based on the search for ways to ensure the harmony of their capabilities and activity requirements during the psychological service, the composition of the individual style in the activity of this person will gradually develop and improve. This, in turn, will not fail to have a positive effect on the social development of the individual and the society.

The merit of K.K. Platonov in creating the methodology of social psychology related to psychological service is that he researched the problem of socio-psychological individuality as the highest level of the manifestation of the individual world of a person and considered the person important for imagining the essence of psychological service not only in his own on the basis of individual characteristics, but also the social content of these individual characteristics scientifically justified the inevitability of maturity by creating conditions based on adequate self-evaluation and development.

In the information of professors: E.G'oziyev, I.Tursunov, J.Ikromov on the subject of "XX century and personality maturity", serious attention is paid to the following situations in the research of the development of the individual, personality and subject, which is of great importance in the provision of psychological services the need to provide: - the main factors and conditions considered as determinants of human development (social, economic, political, legal, ideological, pedagogical and living environment factors); - basic details related to the person himself, his internal conditions, mechanisms, stabilization and involution of belief stages; - the main components of the overall human structure, their interrelationships, a person's response and attitude to external influences, their improvement in the process of development.

In fact, without researching all the spiritual and spiritual experiences of each person in their individual world in accordance with the perspectives of the society in which they live, they ensure the social balance between individual and activity, individual and society, individual and individuality. not

After all, the philosophy of social psychological protection, which is being researched as a means of psychological protection, also requires this. The convenient and extremely important aspects of today's psychological service for personal development have been approved and appreciated by all. However, the special official order from above for the widespread promotion of psychological services and the extreme shortage of practicing psychologists hindered the implementation of the same psychological service in all schools. By the 1990s, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, where feelings of independence, freedom, and self-awareness prevailed, a unique ground was prepared for the wide spread of psychological services, as well as all social spheres aiming at the perfection of man and society. This made it inevitable to move to the next stage of training psychologists in the development of psychological services characteristic of Uzbekistan. Because, it would not be possible to successfully implement psychological services in Uzbekistan without training qualified practitioners-psychologists who can analyze the social and psychological climate in the school.

In accordance with this, first in Tashkent, then in Bukhara, and later in Navoi, Andijan, Samarkand and other regions, retraining courses in the specialty of "practitioner-psychologists" were opened, and those who successfully completed these courses became psychological service supervisors in many schools of our republic. are doing effective work as promoters and researchers.

It is known that psychological services are provided in all countries, even in different scientific and organizational forms. Because, only measures suitable for the socio-economic and political development of each country are used in this country and, if necessary, developed. Accordingly, taking into account the lack of qualified and mature specialists for the development of psychological services in Uzbekistan, the first step began with the initiative to train practicing psychologists from among the most advanced and talented teachers of the school. In this regard, a

reasonable question arises: Why were only experienced teachers involved in the course of "practicing psychologists"?

Indeed, it is not for nothing that only highly qualified pedagogues are involved in the course. Because we think that in order to become a school psychologist, first of all, it is necessary to have the qualifications and experience to analyze the personality of the student, the educational process, and the criteria of education in depth and correctly. There are also social organizational aspects of the issue.

For example, if people who do not have a certain experience working in a school are admitted to the course, they will not be able to acquire the skills to correctly and successfully analyze the pedagogical-psychological process in the school within a period of 4-5 months. On the other hand, if faculties for "practitioner-pedagogue-psychologist" specialty are established in universities and pedagogical institutes, we will have to wait at least in the next few years, maybe even more. Even after graduating from the faculty, without pedagogical experience, it still creates some difficulties in the psychological analysis of the pedagogical process.

Summary. During the research, based on the purpose of these decisions and measures, it was concluded that the initial stage of the organization and development of psychological services in Uzbekistan can be implemented on the basis of the following 7 directions:

1. Psychological service in educational institutions;
2. Psychological service in labor teams;
3. Psychological service in institutions of family life organization system;
4. Psychological service in transport institutions;
5. Psychological service in health care system institutions;
6. Psychological service in institutions of internal affairs, law and order system;
7. Psychological service in sports facilities.

So, today, social psychological activities aimed at ensuring the harmony of the individual psychology and society are being carried out in these 7 directions. First of all, this means that people working in these areas can widely use the social and psychological protection opportunities aimed at self-awareness, knowledge and development, that is, they are less likely to fail in their work and see helps them to work more efficiently.

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